

AWARD EXPECTED RESULTS

 Raising awareness on AWR* context, issues & solutions

Socio-political engagement based on Local Water Forum and networking

Down scaling strategic plan measures into water users every day actions

Test and monitor AWR* in 4 demo cases

Catalogue of AWR* solutions

AWARD DST-TSD** platform to support decision on AWR* solutions

Social Innovation to reconcile technological and non-technological dimensions

Training to assist AWARD's target audiences in changing practices

Exploitation roadmap for AWARD market potential, social impact & policy goals

Multi-scale tailored policy recommendations

 Handbook for integrating AWR* into water supply strategic plan from the 4 demo cases

*AWR: Alternative Water Resources
 **DST-TSD: Deliberation Support Tool for Territorial Sustainable Development

ABOUT AWARD

 36 Months

 3.4 M€ Project Budget

 4 Demo Cases

AWARD aims at enhancing water management by integrating **Alternative Water Resources (AWR) into water supply strategic planning**. The ambition is to provide evidence-based knowledge and lessons learned on the effective integration of affordable, acceptable, and reliable AWR solutions tested and monitored in 4 Demo Cases.

CONTACT US

 www.awardproject.eu

 contact@awardproject.eu

 @AWARD_HEU

PROJECT PARTNERS

16 partners spanning 7 countries

Coordination by **Oieau**
International Office for Water

 universit PARIS-SACLAY

 UNIVERSIT DE VERSAILLES ST-QUENTIN-EN-YVELINES

 ePLANETe Blue

 AQUA

 InterSus
SUSTAINABILITY SERVICES

 B&G
Business Development Group

 aimen
TECHNOLOGIE

 National Technical University of Athens

 IRIDRA

 EOAA

 UT CB
Universitatea Tehnică de Construcții București

 CETAQUA
WATER TECHNOLOGY CENTRE

 ViaQUA

 Citt metropolitana di Milano

 CAP

Alternative Water Resources and deliberation processes to renew water supply strategic planning

AWARD tackles water scarcity and climate change by renewing strategic planning with alternative water resources

ALTERNATIVE WATER RESOURCES (AWR)

AWRs supplement or replace traditional water supplies and regroup sources of water from rainwater harvesting and stormwater storage, treated wastewater (reclaimed water), and the sources of water used in aquifer recharge.

THE AWARD PILLARS

ASSESSMENT FRAMEWORK

Improve Alternatives Water Resources & conventional water assessment framework for water supply strategic planning

SOCIO-POLITICAL ENGAGEMENT

Development of social awareness, policy framework analysis & support for planning

EVIDENCE BASED KNOWLEDGE

Combine evidence based new knowledge from the Demo cases and deliberation support tool for territorial sustainable development

SOCIAL INNOVATION

Consider simultaneously the technological and non-technological (capacity development, governance and business dimensions) AWARD solutions and assess their potential market potential

Purposes

1 Urban

- Aquifer recharge to maintain the level of the lake
- Removal of storm water from sewer network

2 Urban Metropolitan

- Relieve the sewer network
- Ensuring the correct drainage of rainwater

3 Urban Rural

- Irrigation: farming, gardens' hotel, public green spaces, football pitches

4 Industrial

- Irrigation
- Private uses at the industrial park scale

OUR DEMO CASES

- Aquifer recharge
- Storm water
- Rainwater harvesting
- Water reuse

